

Norman Allen Langley Biography by Brian Paul Kaess

Norman 'Norm' Allen Langley was born on April 30, 1905 in Toronto, Ontario, Canada, to John Benjamin Langley and Mary Jane Wilkins. His parents were of English descent and his dad had grown up in Camberwell, London. He was their only child. It appears Norm grew up in Toronto, Canada (in the York Centre neighborhood) and was indoctrinated in the Anglican Faith like his parents. A search was made by the *Diocese of Toronto* (Anglican Church of Canada), but no baptism has ever been found. The Church believes Norm Langley might have attended church at Christ Church in Etobicoke/Mimico in York West, Toronto.

As a baby, he and his mother Mary Jane (Wilkins) Langley took the *Empress of Britain* on July 8, 1906, departing from Quebec, Canada across the Atlantic to Liverpool, England- perhaps to visit family after his birth. The *Empress of Britain* was a sister ship to the *Empress of Ireland*, the latter being lost in 1914. The Langley's appear again in the 1911 Canada Census, just one year before the fateful *Titanic* sinking in 1912. He also appears in the 1921 Canada Census.

Norm came as a young man to America (specifically Chicago) in 1924 through Port Huron, Michigan, and later made his living as a truck driver. He was a longtime resident of Chicago. He stated he worked for Standard Oil at one point during his career, but this may have been a subsidiary. He was married multiple times (four at last count), including Mildred Langley, Mary Parkin, Thelma Pearl (Anderson) Schultze, & Margaret Jane (Swartz) Dawson. His most beloved wife appeared to be Thelma because he always spoke fondly of her and was buried next to her in Rosehill Cemetery, Chicago.

Norm was a U.S. Army Veteran from WWII, and stated he had served abroad in England and North Africa. It appears even though Norm was a Canadian, he volunteered to fight for the Yanks. He recalled V2 bombs flying over the English Channel and making a buzzing noise before they struck. Coming home, he must have had a renascent glow in his heart. He kept many Veteran-style publications on his coffee table in his living room such as *VFW*, *American Legion*, *DAV*, as well as *Model Railroading*. This suggested he was a member of these organizations. He was an avid model railroader & kept a train set and homemade model railroad in his basement. It fell into disrepair, yet still fascinated. He was a wiley figure and ingratiated himself with the twins who 'took' to Norm. He was on friendly terms with Winifred 'Win' Gillis, and would shop at *Carl's Meat Market*, where Win worked as a butcher.

Norm's favorite line was: 'the bigger they are, the harder they fall!' Garret Kaess once said, 'I remember I got him a small item that said, "world's best grandfather" on it. When I gave it to him, he had tears in his eyes. Only time I remember him tearing up. Dude was cool.'

Norm had at least one son, John 'Jack' Allen Langley, who family lore said was a U.S. Army veteran from the Vietnam War who had been wounded by grenade shrapnel while sleeping in his bunk. Probate Specialist Juli Claussen helped verify the existence of his son, his last known address (2024) being in Merriville, Indiana. 'He (John A Langley) has a close association with the late Margaret J Langley', per Juli. It also turned out his son Jack was a U.S. Marine in Vietnam, shipping out sometime from MCRD San Diego in 1967. Research on Norm's family is still fluid.

Norm owned a two-story house (with attic) on 1629 Hollywood Ave. in Chicago's Edgewater neighborhood during the 1970's. This lot had an iver-covered garage. This may have been passed down to him from his wife Thelma's parents, the Anderson's (of Swedish descent)- how fitting for someone who lived so close to Andersonville, Chicago. He took the twins once to suburban Chicagoland (Carpentersville or Romeosville?) to visit his son and his granddaughters. It was a playful time. He also loved cats and dogs, of which the former he had many. He was known for taking his dogs for walks, even in the snow. He enjoyed watching 70's TV shows such as *Ba Ba Black Sheep*, *the Muppet Show*, *the Six Million Dollar Man*, *the Bionic Woman*, *the Love Boat* & *Fantasy Island*. He liked to 'hide the brandy' from Margaret while he secretly sipped. Margaret would chide him, 'Norman, Norman- you can't do that!' Perhaps this habit was the cause of him undergoing successful vein surgery in his right leg in his retirement. In his final years, he was married to Margaret (she said they married about 1976) and he helped drive her twin grandsons to private school in the mornings in his yellow, four-door sedan.

Norm had a heart attack on May 22,1980, which was the cause of his death in the next few hours. It had been a bright, warm, Spring day before he began to falter late in the evening. His last words were, 'Margaret, I think I'm going to die tonight!' He was taken by *Chicago Fire Dept.* (CFD) paramedics to the ICU at Edgewater Hospital (later Edgewater Medical Center) but succumbed to his sickness. Dr. Maynulet, our neighbor, tried to comfort him, but could little to stop his decline. Grandma Margaret came home the next day and told the twins simply: 'Norm died last night.'

He was buried in Rosehill Cemetery next to his previous wife Thelma. Margaret inherited the house and proceeds from a life insurance company, which balked at paying, but was forced to under legal pressure by her attorney Mr. Jackson. Margaret eventually sold Norm's house to a Romanian family in 1988. Norm was beloved for being an old wise-acre and for poking fun at people and being a role model to the young.